

Comparison of Aerobic Capacity among Overweight and Non-Overweight Postpartum Women's

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Abstract:- Post-delivery increased weight can cause intergenerational harm, negatively affecting a mother's cardiovascular and cardiopulmonary health. Cardiopulmonary exercise testing defines maximum aerobic capacity through measurement of VO₂max. VO₂max values have important role in informing patients' selection for advance obesity intervention. Aim - to know difference between aerobic capacity in overweight and non-overweight women. Method- 40 patient of age 18-30y; 20 overweight women with BMI >25 and women with BMI <25. The patients were asked to stepping bench for total duration 3 min. Result- This showed extremely significant improvement in VO₂Max and BORG Scale. Conclusion – This study suggest that overweight postpartum women had significantly reduced aerobic capacity when compared with non-overweight postpartum women.

Keywords:- Body Mass Index, Aerobic Capacity, Exertional Dyspnea, VO₂Max, Postpartum Women.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy has been identified as a length of threat for immoderate weight gain main to lengthy-time period weight retention and maternal weight problems. numerous research has suggested will increase in maternal frame weight ranging from 1.5 to 3kg above pre-being pregnant weight while postpartum weight is measured as much as 18 months postpartum, and from 0.5 to 6.2 kg while measured 2.5y–15y postpartum. [5]. The prevalence of obesity among postpartum women was over 40%. During childhood and adolescence, remarkable physiological, anatomical, and psychological transformations that affect physical fitness are caused by growth, maturation, and development. Physical fitness is a key idea in (clinical) exercise physiology and can be thought of as an integrated measure of most, if not all, of the body functions involved in daily physical activity and exercise[6]. Aerobic fitness, body composition, muscular strength, power, speed, balance, flexibility, and hand-eye coordination are examples of these body functions. [7].

One of the most crucial aspects of physical fitness is aerobic fitness. Adults with cardiovascular and pulmonary diseases, as well as healthy adults, have been shown to have lower morbidity and mortality rates when their aerobic fitness is higher^[12,13]. Aerobic fitness has also been found to be a significant health indicator in adolescents. For instance, total adiposity and cardiovascular risk factors have been found to be inversely correlated with aerobic fitness ^[15].

The objective of cardiopulmonary exercise testing (CPET) is to evaluate a patient's functional capacity as well as the coordination of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems' physiological performance. One of the most common signs for which a cardiopulmonary exercise test is requested is unexplained dyspnoea on exertion (DOE) ^[8]. Exertional dyspnea can be caused by a variety of illness-related abnormalities, deconditioning alone or obesity alone, or both ^[9, 11]. In patients with dyspnea on exertion, physiological responses to exercise may be completely normal, or in many severe cases, patients may also be obese, greatly complicating the assessment of exercise limitations and the potential mechanisms of dyspnea on exertion. In order to investigate and uncover the mechanisms underlying dyspnea on exertion in otherwise healthy obese adults and clinical patients with both disease and obesity, this article will cover CPET^[17].

In clinical practice, the complementary test known as CPET is becoming an increasingly important tool for examining cardiovascular diseases. Assessment of cardiorespiratory fitness, assistance with the investigation and follow-up of patients with myocardial ischemia, objective prescription of training zones (in healthy individuals and patients with cardiac diseases), and differential diagnosis of dyspnea are just a few of the well-established uses for CPET. The groundworks of the CPET depend on a ventilatory examination of the breathed out gases, determined to evaluate the utilization of oxygen (VO₂), the development of carbon dioxide (VCO₂), and minute ventilation very still and during activity and recuperation^[22]. The identification of functional capacity and the pathophysiologic responses during the rest-to-exercise transition are valuable information provided.

A precise evaluation of aerobic power and cardiometabolic variables at submaximal and maximal effort levels (for example: ventilatory edge), and Assessment of ventilatory effectiveness. Despite the fact that its initial purpose was to more precisely identify functional capacity, particularly in heart failure and the differential diagnosis of dyspnea^[22], It is well known that living an active lifestyle is beneficial. A large number of these advantages are likewise connected with more significant levels of cardiorespiratory wellness (VO₂max) which might apply defensive impacts that are free of conventional gamble factors. Additionally, even a modest increase in fitness can have significant health benefits for those who are not physically fit.

During a progressive cardiopulmonary exercise test up to maximal exertion, the measurement of maximal VO₂ (VO₂max) or peak VO₂ (VO₂peak) is widely regarded as the gold standard for evaluating aerobic fitness^[18,19]. Important information that can be used for (differential) diagnostic, prognostic, and evaluative purposes in medicine is provided by the noninvasive and dynamic nature of the measurements that are carried out during cardiopulmonary exercise testing^[20]. Adults with chronic conditions, in contrast to healthy adults, frequently limit their participation in sport and physical activity programs due to perceived or actual limitations imposed by their condition.^[20]

Although physical activity is an important part of treating and preventing obesity^[21], exertional dyspnea prevents many obese people from exercising regularly^[22]. Even in the absence of comorbidities, exertional dyspnoea may be caused by a number of obesity-related limitations at rest and during exercise. These limitations are discussed in the following sections. The CPET method is a good way to examine potential causes of dyspnea on exertion in otherwise healthy adults by assessing multiple systems during exercise stress^[17]. The significance of aerobic capacity in daily life to design the treatment convention in overweight post pregnancy ladies. to avoid the negative effects of postpartum weight gain. To figure out the distinction in high-impact limit among overweight and ordinary weight ladies. to determine the aerobic capacity of postpartum overweight women.

II. AIM AND OBJECTIVE

- *Aim*- To know exercise capacity in overweight postpartum women.
- *Objective*- Evaluate aerobic capacity in overweight postpartum women and comparing it with that of normal weight postpartum women.
- *Hypothesis*
 - *Null Hypothesis*- No any difference in aerobic capacity in overweight and normal weight postpartum women.
 - *Alternate Hypothesis*- Difference of aerobic capacity in overweight and normal weight postpartum women.

III. METHODOLOGY

Study design: Randomized Control Trial **Study type:** Cross sectional **Study duration:** 6 months. **Sample size:** 60 patients

Sampling method: Random sampling **Place of study:** NPCRC OPD **Study population:** Postpartum women with BMI >25 and BMI <25.

IV. CRITERIA FOR STUDY

Inclusion Criteria- Patients with overweight., Postpartum women., Patients with BMI >25 and BMI <25, Patients who are willing to participate. And Age –18-30year

Exclusion Criteria- Patients who are unwilling to participate., Age <18 and >30, Patients with no other cardiopulmonary disorder. And Patient with no other postpartum consequences

V. PROCEDURE

The present cross-sectional study was carried out after taking due permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee. The study was conducted to compare aerobic capacity among non-overweight and overweight postpartum women. According to inclusion and exclusion criteria consent were taken from participants and selected. Total 60 number of patients were taken and make two groups each contain 30 participants, group A (non-overweight postpartum women) group B (overweight postpartum women). Estimation of VO₂ max by queens college step test – It was performed using stepping bench with 16.25 inches height.

Stepping was done for total duration of 3 min at the rate of 22 steps ups/min. After completion of exercise pulse rate was measured from 5th to 20th second of recovery period. It was converted into pulse rate per minute^[11].

Following equation as described along with the procedure in McArdle, Katch and Katch's Exercise Physiology was used to estimate VO₂ max expressed in milliliters per kilogram body weight per minute^[11].

$$\text{VO}_2 \text{ max (ml/kg/min)} = 65.81 - (0.1847 \times \text{pulse rate in beats/ min})$$

Fig 1- Shapiro-Wilk Test

Data analysis was done using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 21). Basic descriptions were presented in the form of mean and Standard deviation. The data were assessed for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Independent Sample 't' test was used to analyze the differences between non overweight and overweight women. Borg scale was compared using Mann Whitney 'U' test. The level of significance was set at p < 0.05 for all tests

- *Outcome Measures*
VO₂Max. And Borg Scale

VI. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Information investigation was finished involving the Measurable Bundle for Sociologies (SPSS adaptation 21). Essential depictions were introduced as mean and Standard deviation. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to determine whether the data were normal. The independent sample t test was used to compare and contrast women who were neither overweight nor obese. The Mann Whitney "U" test was used to compare the Borg scale. For each test, the significance level was set at p 0.05.

VII. RESULT

Consequence of this study was dissected as far as decreased VO2 Max and BORG Score. The independent sample t test was used to compare postpartum women who were not overweight to overweight women. The Mann Whitney "U" test was used to compare the Borg scale. For each test, the significance level was set at p 0.05. BORG Scale and VO2Max both showed significant improvements as a result.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Groups	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Non Overweight				
Age	21.00	30.00	25.66	2.49
BMI	20.20	24.70	23.35	0.86
VO ₂ Max	35.10	42.30	37.56	1.78
Borg Scale	1.00	5.00	2.90	1.21
Overweight				
Age	21.00	30.00	26.93	2.28
BMI	24.60	30.00	27.32	1.62
VO ₂ Max	32.70	35.30	34.08	0.81
Borg Scale	3.00	7.00	5.13	1.56

Table 2: Comparison of parameters between Non Overweight and Overweight women.

Site	Mean ± SD	Mean Difference	t Value	P value
Age				
Non Overweight	25.66 ± 2.49	1.26	2.049	0.045*
Overweight	26.93 ± 2.28			
BMI				
Non Overweight	23.35 ± 0.86	3.97	11.825	< 0.001*
Overweight	27.32 ± 1.62			
VO₂ Max				
Non Overweight	37.56 ± 1.78	3.48	9.730	< 0.001*
Overweight	34.08 ± 0.81			

Independent Sample 't' Test: *P < 0.05 (significant), **p > 0.05 (Not significant)

Table 3: Comparison of Borg scale between Non Overweight and Overweight women

Groups	Mean ± SD	Median	Z Value	P value
Borg Scale				
Non Overweight	2.90 ± 1.21	3.00	4.803	< 0.001*
Overweight	5.13 ± 1.56	5.00		

Mann Whitney 'U' test, P < 0.05 (significant), P > 0.05 (Not significant)

VIII. DISCUSSION

In the current study, overweight young women's VO2 Max was found to be significantly lower than that of women of normal weight. This indicates that overweight young women have a significantly lower capacity to complete demanding tasks. Even in overweight females who are below the BMI threshold of 30 kg/m2 required to be classified as obese, a decrease in cardiopulmonary fitness is a significant warning sign. However, it can be explained by looking at how excess fatty tissue affects the physiology of the heart and

lungs, which has been studied in a number of studies on overweight and obese people.

BMI and the duration of obesity have been found to be correlated with cardiac function. This means the significance of early recognition and mediation at a beginning phase to forestall the heart illness in overweight/corpulent people. The respiratory system is negatively impacted by obesity, which results in a deviation in respiratory mechanics, a decrease in the endurance and strength of the respiratory muscles, a decrease in the amount of gas exchanged, and restrictions on lung function and exercise capacity. Adipose tissue

accumulation in the abdominal cavity and chest wall may compress the thoracic cage, diaphragm, and lungs, resulting in impairment of lung function. Lung compliance and diaphragm displacement may be restricted as a result of this. Lung volumes decrease as a result. [31-35]

We used a sample of 60 people from groups A and B, each with 30 people between the ages of 18 and 30 who had a BMI between 25 and 25. These women were put through a three-minute step-up test. As outcome measures, the BORG Scale and VO₂Max were utilized. Non-overweight women had a mean VO₂Max value of 37.56, while overweight women had a mean value of 34.08; The standard deviation for VO₂Max for women who were not overweight was 1.78, while the standard deviation for women who were overweight was 0.81. The BORG Scale for women who were not overweight was 1.21, while the BORG Scale for women who were overweight was 1.56. The fact that the VO₂Max and BORG Scale p values were less than 0.001 indicates that the result was highly significant. The cross-sectional design of this study prevents it from commenting on the cause-and-effect relationship between overweight status and aerobic capacity status. Bigger and longitudinal investigations should be finished to additional the figuring out regarding the matter. In order to determine whether weight loss can improve cardiopulmonary efficiency in obese patients, interventional studies can be helpful.

To sum up the lower oxygen consuming limit in overweight females might be an early mark of cardio-respiratory brokenness. We can speculate that obesity has a negative impact on VO₂ max because it may reduce one's capacity to maximally consume oxygen. As a result, primary prevention measures are required to manage the overweight/obesity syndrome.

IX. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that aerobic capacity of overweight postpartum women is less than non-overweight postpartum women. There was noticeable difference in VO₂Max and BORG Scale

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